

ASSESSMENT OF THE RELIABILITY OF COSTUME FABRICS

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Abstract: In this research work, using modern equipment, the qualitative characteristics of costume fabrics developed from various fibrous compositions were studied and significant indicators of the test samples were determined to assess the reliability characteristics.

Keywords: costume fabric, breaking load, incommunicability, abrasion, stiffness, breathability, reliability.

Quality and reliability are the main requirements that the consumer or customer has for any product, including textiles. This is especially important for fabrics used for clothing. Reliability is generally understood to mean the ability of a material (article) to perform a given function while maintaining its performance within a given range during the desired operating time.

Their appearance (surface smoothness, gloss, natural color) and properties depend on the fibrous composition of fabrics: strength, elongation, elasticity, thermal conductivity, hygroscopicity, shrinkage, and others. Knowing the composition of fabrics and the properties of the fibers from which they are made makes it possible to determine the purpose of fabrics, their behavior in the process of making clothes and its operation (sliding of fabrics during cutting, sprinkling and spreading threads in the seams, shrinkage, wrinkling, dimensional stability, etc.), as well as modes of wet-thermal cutting of garments

Costume fabrics occupy one of the most important values in the production of everyday and festive clothes for women, men and children. Therefore, the requirements for products must be determined from the relationships of the system "clothing - human - surrounding costume fabrics, the fibrous composition of raw materials, the properties of fibers, their interaction, as well as their influence on the physical and mechanical properties of the product during its production, transportation, storage and operation are separately taken into account.

The objects of research in this work were the following samples of costume fabrics: I - 70% wool fibers + 30% viscose fibers, II - 70% wool fibers + 30%

synthetic fibers, III - 100% cotton fibers, IV - 40% polyester fibers + 60% cotton fibers, V -65% synthetic fibers + 35% viscose fibers.

Physical and mechanical characteristics of costume fabrics of different fibrous composition

№	Name of indicators	Fibrous composition				
		70% wool fibers 30% viscose fibers	70% wool fibers 30% synthetic fibers	100% cotton fibers	40% polyester fibers 60% cotton fibers	65% synthetic fibers 35% viscose fibers
1.	Surface density, g/m ² ,	227,7	225,6	223,4	221,8	220,3
2.	Thickness, mm	0,4	0,5	0,5	0,3	0,5
4.	Wrinkle resistance of the fabric, % by warp	73,2	78,1	43,2	68,8	79,3
	weft`	69,8	68,1	48,6	65,3	71,8
5.	Breaking load, N by warp	221,5	766	996	983	868
	Weft	194,2	513	513	618	713
6.	Elongation,% by warp	38,7	35,6	18,5	20,5	29,1
	Weft	27,0	29,8	26,3	26,4	36,8
7.	Abrasion, cycle	22300	245000	21000	23000	28000
8.	Fabric stiffness by warp	3050	3256	4678	8541	2938
	weft	4222	5103	10478,8	10160	8064
9.	Air permeability, sm ³ /sm ² ·sek	17,07	22,53	30,92	38,44	17,82
10	Hygroscopicity, %	3,13	5,16	13,20	5,03	0,22

Sample № 3 has the highest breaking load on the base, which is 27.6% more than sample No. 1, 23.9% more than sample № 2, 1.3% more than sample № 4 and 12.8% more than sample № 5. The breaking load on the weft of sample No. 5 is the highest value and is 713N.

In terms of tensile elongation by base, the largest value in sample № 1 is 8.01% more than in sample № 2 by 52.2% more than in sample № 3 by 47.0% more than in sample № 4 and by 24.8% more than in sample № 5. The largest value of the weft elongation is sample No. 5 and is 36.8%

The effect of fibrous composition on the rigidity of costume fabrics can be seen here on the basis of sample № 4 the highest value, the weft stiffness of sample № 3 is more than the rest of the samples is 10478.8, which is 59.7% more than sample No. 1 by 51.3% more than 2 samples by 3.03% more than 4 samples and 23.03% more than 5 samples.

In terms of nonministrability in duck, sample № 5 is 71.8%, which is 2.8% more than sample № 1, 5.1% more than sample №2, 32.3% more than sample No. 3 and 90.5% more than sample № 4.

In terms of air permeability, sample №4 has the highest value, hygroscopicity in sample No. 3 is 13.2%, which is 76.3% more than sample № 1, 60.9% more than sample No. 2, 61.9% more than sample № 4 and 90% more than sample № 5.

In terms of abrasion, sample No. 5 is the highest indicator and is 28,000 cycles, which is 20.3% more than sample №1, 12.5% more than sample № 2, 25% more than sample № 3, 17.8% more than sample № 4.

To assess the quality and reliability of the studied tissues, an expert survey was conducted as a result of which the most significant indicators affecting the reliability of costume fabrics used in statistical management were determined [3]. Each expert is offered a questionnaire in which he evaluates each proposed characteristic to the appropriate ranks. The most important is assigned the rank $R = 1$, the following is assigned the rank 2, etc. The following key figures were selected:

- X1- air permeability
- X2- hygroscopicity
- X3- abrasion resistance
- X4- breaking load
- X5- color stability
- X6- stiffness
- X7- inconsistency
- X8- thickness

X9- shrinkage

X10- interlacing

After statistical processing of the research results, we got the following:

Significant indicators turned out to be

X3 - abrasion resistance = 0.30

X4- breaking load = 0.35

X6- stiffness = 0.35

X8- thickness = 0.19

With these values, it is possible to conduct a comparative assessment of the reliability of the tissues under study. Sample 4 (60% cotton and 40% PE) is the best in terms of reliability of the breaking load of fabrics, followed by sample 3 (100% cotton), then sample 5 (65% synthetic fibers + 35% viscose), sample 2 (70% wool + 30% synthetic) and sample 1 (70% wool + 30% viscose).

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